

Heavy Metal Concentrations in plants growing on Solid Waste Disposal Site, Oja-Oba, Lagos State

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Abstract

The study investigated the heavy metal concentration in plants obtained from Oja-Oba; one of the solid waste disposal sites in Lagos, Nigeria. Plant samples were collected and then analyzed for heavy metals using Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS). The findings from the study showed that the studied plants bio accumulated lead, copper and cadmium. For instance, 0.34 ± 0.05 lead concentration and 0.27 ± 0.05 cadmium concentration respectively, were found in *Capsicum frutescens*. In this same plant, the concentrations of copper was below the acceptable limit. Also, the concentrations of lead, copper and cadmium in other studied plants were found to be below the WHO maximum permissible limit. This implies that poor waste management and accumulation of tons of solid waste in the dumpsite negatively affects soil quality, plants that are likely to grow on the dumpsites as well as animals within the food chain that would feed on such plants. Hence, the resultant effects could pose serious threat to human and animal health due to possible bioaccumulation and bio magnifications through plant uptake from the soil. It was recommended that proper waste management using the 3Rs (reduce, reuse and recycle), appropriate environmental laws must be in place and sanitary landfills should be available to ensure the sustainability of the environment.

Keywords: Bioaccumulation, concentrations, dumpsite, heavy metals, solid waste

1.0 Introduction

Heavy metals are elements categorized by high density and are not easily biodegradable [1]. [2] reported that soil pH is the major factor affecting metal availability in soil. Availability of heavy metals like cadmium and zinc to the roots of plants like *Thlaspi caerulescens* decreases with increased in soil pH [3]. Organic matter and hydrous ferric oxide have been shown to decrease heavy metal availability through immobilization of these metals [4]. Significant positive correlations have also been recorded between heavy metals and some soil physical properties such as moisture content and

water holding capacity [5]. The heavy metals that are available for plant uptake are those that are present as soluble components in the soil solution or those that are easily solubilized by root exudates [6]. Although plants require certain heavy metals for their growth and upkeep, excessive amounts of these metals can become toxic to plants. The ability of plants to accumulate essential metals equally enables them to acquire other nonessential metals [6]. Although metals are needed in living organisms especially trace elements; however, when the quantities found in a living organism exceeds the expected amount then it could pose potential danger [1]. According to [7] heavy metal contamination of

the soil has been seen as great challenge, and pose great risk to humans, plants and food supply globally. [8] reported that the combination of lead (Pb) and copper (Cu) at both high concentration (1000 mg/kg each) and low concentration (500 mg/kg) resulted in a rapid and complete death of the leaves and stem of *Lythrum salicaria*. The persistent, accumulative nature of solid wastes, plants growing on them, and possible subsequent consumption of these plants by herbivores, especially domestic ones like goats, necessitates this study. Hence, it is essential to evaluate heavy metal concentrations in plants found on one of the dumpsites in Lagos, Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Location

Geologic Setting of Oja-Oba Lagos falls between $N6^{\circ}62'$ to $N6^{\circ}65'$ and $E3^{\circ}28'$ to $E3^{\circ}32'$ within the eastern Dahomey Basin of southwestern Nigeria in Alimosho Local Government Area of Lagos State (Figures 1 and Plate 1). Lagos is basically a sedimentary area, it is located within the Western Nigeria coastal zone, a zone of coastal creeks and lagoons developed by barrier beaches associated with sand deposition

Figure 1: Map of the study location

Plate 1: Oja-Oba dumpsite

2.2 Plant Samples

Random sampling technique was employed to collect the plant samples of Chilli pepper (*Capsicum frutescens*), Milkweed (*Euphorbia heterophylla*) and Mary Grass (*Setaria barbata*) (Plate 2, 3 and 4), at Oja-Oba solid waste disposal site. The leaves of the plant samples were separated from the whole plant with the aid of a stainless-steel knife and labelled appropriately.

Plate 2: Typical Pepper (*Capsicum frutescens*)

Plate 3: Milkweed (*Euphorbia heterophylla*)

Plate 4: Mary Grass (*Setaria barbata*)

2.3 Plant and Soil Sample Preparation and Digestion

After treatment, in order to check the level of metal removal, the plants and soil samples were taken to the laboratory for heavy metal analysis. Each plant sample was separated into leaves, roots, and stems and then dried at 50°C for 8 hours in an oven [9]. The several methods used for the metal analysis followed the procedures employed by [1].

3.0 Results and Discussion

The concentrations (mg/kg) of Copper (Cu), Lead (Pb) and Cadmium (Cd) of the studied plant samples are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Heavy metal concentrations in selected plants

Heavy metals	Concentrations (mgkg ⁻¹) in Milkweed (<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>) (Mean± SD)	Concentrations (mgkg ⁻¹) in Mary Grass (<i>Setaria barbata</i>) (Mean± SD)	Concentrations (mgkg ⁻¹) in Pepper (<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>) (Mean± SD)	WHO/FAO Maximum Permissible value (mgkg ⁻¹)
Cu	1.25± 0.03	1.22± 0.02	7.25± 0.01	73.3
Pb	0.29± 0.12	0.20± 0.04	0.34± 0.05	0.3
Cd	0.16± 0.01	0.19± 0.01	0.27± 0.01	0.2

**Values are in triplicates

From Table 1 above, lead (Pb) and Cadmium (Cd) accumulation in all studied plants were found to be lower than that of copper (Cu) in all the three studied plants. However, the concentration of lead and cadmium accumulated, were found to be higher than the WHO permissible limits for *Capsicum frutescens*. In this same plant, the concentrations of copper though higher than in other plants, was below the acceptable limit. Also, the concentrations of lead, copper and cadmium in other studied plants were found to be below the WHO maximum permissible limit. The accumulation of metals within these plants must have been done through their roots as reported by [11] that the capacities to absorb ionic compounds within plants from the soil at low concentrations, is through their roots system. Researchers like [12], [13] and [14] have observed that the mechanisms of heavy metals take up and translocation in plants have been adopted by plants in response to heavy metal toxicity. The results in Table 1 indicated that Cd had the lowest metal concentration/accumulation. This is corroborated by the reports by [15] that Pb has the ability to form compounds that are insoluble in the soil, hence its reduced mobility and bioavailability while Cd is highly soluble in water. Hence, Cd can be easily removed from the soil by soil washing [15].

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

Findings from this study, show that the soils at the dump sites and plants been studied are contaminated by heavy metals. These pose a lot of threat to plant and animal health. It is therefore recommended that the plants used for this study would be useful in phytoremediation of heavy metal contaminated/polluted sites. Also, animals or humans feasting on these plants from the dump sites should desist from this and measures to ensure this should be in place.

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